

Conceptual components of medical and health discourse (using the concept of "Health" as an example)

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Abstract: The article contains an overview of such concepts as “discourse”, “concept”, provides approaches to the definition of these definitions, and examines the conceptual components of discourse.

Key words: discourse, concept, medical discourse, concept "Health" , phenomenon.

Today, the connections between linguistics and related sciences are expanding and multiplying, facilitating the emergence of new areas of research. An example of such integration is medical linguistics, which is of an applied nature, since the identification and description of the structural-semantic, lingua-stylistic features of medical texts is of direct importance for improving the theory of languages, translating foreign-language specialized literature, and professionally oriented training of doctors in foreign languages. Theoretical and practical issues of medical discourse are studied by S. S. Barbasheva [1:1441-1444], Zh. N. Makusheva [2:108-111], the specifics of the organization and communicative-speech classification of medical English-language text are presented in the works of I. A. Menshenina, L. S. Shuravina, and others.

Modern society, concerned about its own health and the health of its children, increasingly turns to such sources for help in trying to find answers to its questions and faces the challenge of understanding specific medical discourse. The relevance of this topic is driven by the growing interest in medical discourse; parents' need to access websites and forums dedicated to children's health; the emergence of online consultations on health issues; the lack of time for medical specialists and the difficulty of making a diagnosis; and modern society's interest in a healthy lifestyle.

Popular scientific medical discourse is a hybrid communicative entity. Its subject matter encompasses communication on topics related to health maintenance, disease prevention, and treatment—that is, medical topics. Such communication is professionally conducted in medical institutions by specially trained individuals with medical education, who act as representatives of medicine as a social institution. This communication format can be appropriately termed professional medical discourse. Alongside it, common medical discourse is also common, and we all participate in it

when discussing issues related to health and disease. Advertising medical discourse, which promotes certain medical products and services, is also widespread. At the same time, doctors often speak to the public, explaining healthy lifestyle norms and recommending various disease prevention methods. In this context, we encounter popular medical discourse. Its disseminators include not only medical professionals but also media representatives, who act as intermediaries between professionally trained specialists and the general public. Popular medical discourse, in this regard, represents a hybrid formation between medical and media discourse, which naturally influences the conceptual specificity of medical discourse. Experts' explanations of health-related issues for the general public are noteworthy.

This article examines one of the central medical concepts, the concept of "health." Currently, the scientific literature contains over one hundred definitions of health, reflecting approaches from various sciences. As a universal value, health is crucial to a person's entire life. The concept of health is an abstract one. It is not a concrete object that a person can see, hear, or touch. However, people perceive its importance through figurative concepts, viewing health as a valuable asset—wealth, treasure, gold. A person's physiological and psychological state is recognized as the most important aspect of their life.

Modern explanatory dictionaries, emphasizing the dual nature of the lexeme "health," for the first time record the terminological use of the word: "1. Biological and Medical. A state of the body characterized by the proper functioning of all its organs, as well as complete balance with the environment. To take care of one's health. Harmful to health, etc. 2. The general physical condition of the human body, well-being. To inquire about one's grandmother's health" [3:101-110]

Thus, we can conclude that the concept of "Health" is a multidimensional phenomenon, reflecting in everyday consciousness the idea of the dual (physical and mental) state of the organism, the assessment of which is carried out from the point of view of an external observer, as well as the internal self-awareness of the subject, the bearer of the state.

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